

Project¹ Number: 660067

Project Acronym: COLD μ WAVE

Project title: Energy Innovative Food Process For The Production Of High Quality Frozen
Food

Design and description of the prototype MW blanching equipment

¹ The term ‘project’ used in this template equates to an ‘action’ in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

According to the DoA of COLDMWAVE proposal, during the implementation of Work Package 1, the design of the Microwave Blancher will be delivered.

- a) **A prototype MW heating equipment without turntable** was designed and constructed for the needs of the computational model validation of MW blanching of fruits (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic description of the components of the experimental set-up. All components are based on WR340 standard waveguides.

The microwave heating equipment consists of:

- α) a microwave head (Dipolar power supply + magnetron + waveguide transition) (Figure 3),

Figure 3.

- β) an isolator (National 2722 162 11171) and a resonant ring microwave switch, (Figure 4)

Figure 4.

γ) an auto-tuner (Homer STHT V1.5) (Figure 5),

Figure 5.

δ) a three-stub and finally one piece of waveguide with a single stub (Figure 6) that connects to the modified domestic microwave oven (Figure 7).

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

The three-stub and the single stub together enable customized matching (i.e. reflection of microwave power) between the load and the rest of the system, while the isolator isolates the magnetron from the system thanks to a water load. In this setup, the autotuner is only used for its ability to measure forward and reflected power. The auto tuner was connected with a PC where with the use of Homsoft software the incident and the reflected were logged in real time. The role of microwave switch is to enable removal of the initial full power peak that starts every new cycle of microwave power generation (necessary for the power supply to start up the magnetron). Generated microwave power is computer-controlled by customized software in the approximate range 50 – 800 W.

Figure 8.

An fiber optic temperature sensor with 4 optical fibers was connected with a PC where the temperature in 4 different locations was able to be logged.

The inner dimensions of the cavity of the microwave oven are 29.5 cm x 31.5 cm x 20 cm (width x depth x height).